

Sentiment Analysis of Customer Reviews Using Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing Methods

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Abstract

The study aims to design a system using natural language processing (NLP) methods from machine learning for sentiment analysis via Twitter. This system will classify comments from customers who have used airline services, to analyze and categorize their sentiments. By analyzing the comments of customers who have used airline services, the aim is to improve the experiences of both customers and companies. The selected tweets will be classified as positive, negative, or neutral, and sentiment analysis will be conducted based on the results. Additionally, efforts will be made to predict which department within a company a comment is related to. Data will be obtained from the social media platform Twitter, and a sentiment analysis report will be produced using NLP. The Twitter API will be used for the application, leveraging Python libraries that utilize NLP methods.

Keywords: machine learning, sentiment analysis, nlp

Introduction

In today's world, ensuring passenger satisfaction in air travel, one of the most preferred modes of transportation, plays a significant role due to the increasing number of competing airlines. It is believed that the processes required to operate a flight affect passenger satisfaction. Given the importance for airlines to understand how all stages experienced during a flight impact passenger satisfaction, this study aims to examine the effects of service quality before, during, and after the flight separately. With the advent of social media applications on mobile phones, our social lives are transitioning to a virtual environment. Today, social media platforms (such as Facebook, Twitter, etc.), which are very popular and allow people to quickly and easily share their opinions about any product or service, have seen a parallel increase in content with the widespread use of the internet. Studies on Twitter indicate that as technology advances, users' interest in Twitter increases. In our country, Twitter is used not only as a social media application but also to express complaints and specific situations. The aim of this study is to design a system using natural language processing (NLP) methods from machine learning for sentiment analysis via Twitter. All processes were carried out using the Python programming language. This system will classify comments from customers who have used airline services to analyze and categorize their sentiments. By analyzing the comments of customers who have used airline services, the aim is to improve the experiences of both customers and companies. The selected tweets will be classified as positive, negative, or neutral, and sentiment analysis will be conducted based on the results. Additionally, efforts will be made to predict which department within a company a comment is related to. Data will be obtained from the social media platform Twitter, and a sentiment analysis report will be produced using NLP. The Twitter API will be used for the application, leveraging Python libraries that utilize NLP methods.

Method

Data

To perform sentiment analysis, it is necessary to collect and analyze data related to written or spoken texts, sentences, articles, audio, and even images. The collected data is examined using different analysis methods depending on the type of data, and the results indicate what the data means and what kind of sentiment it contains. For the dataset, the social media platform X (formerly known as Twitter) has been preferred. As it is a platform where users share their real-time thoughts, feelings, and reactions, it has been evaluated as a suitable data repository for sentiment analysis. Users have been selected from individuals who have previously received services from airlines in Turkey. The X API has been used to

retrieve tweets shared by users through specific keywords, hashtags, or user accounts. These retrieved tweets are labeled data deemed sufficient for training models and performing sentiment analysis. A total of 3052 user tweets were collected, and additionally, 889 equally labeled synthetic data were generated.

Table 1. Example customer tweets on airline services

Customer Tweets Example
Esenboğa havalimanı çalışanlarına ne olmuş böyle insanlara bağırıp işlemleri çok yavaş alıyorlar. yönlendirdiler orada uçak kalkana kadar müşteri hizmetlerine bağlanmaya çalıştım yine bağlanamadım
Rötarlı, aç,susuz iyi oldu.Çok keyif aldık rötar olmadan sefer düzenleyemez misiniz kuzum siz?
Harika Lezzetler eşliğinde keyifle yeni maceralara devam ediyoruz... şimdiki rotamız
Uçak içi hijyen genellikle ön planda, ama bazı durumlarda daha titiz bir temizlik bekliyorum.
Uçuşlarınızın güvenliği genellikle öncelikli, ama bazı durumlarda daha fazla güvenlik önlemi bekliyorum

Data Normalization

After collecting user comments using the X API, the text preprocessing phase was initiated to analyze these comments. Text preprocessing is a process that leaves only meaningful words in sentences. In this phase, customer tweets were labeled as positive, negative, and neutral. Punctuation marks, emojis, slang, offensive language, and unnecessary words were removed from the text, leaving only meaningful words. As a result of these operations, the texts were made more suitable for natural language processing (NLP) analyses.

Table 2. Customer tweet before and after data preprocessing

Raw tweet / After Data preprocessing	
Before Normalization	After Normalization
167. #THY'nin geniş iç mekanı ferah bir atmosfer sunuyor. 🌞	geniş iç mekanı ferah atmosfer sunuyor

Tokenization, one of the natural language processing techniques, is the process of parsing each word (token) in a sentence. Breaking the sentence into tokens allows the models to understand and analyze the text better. After tokenizing customer tweets, the lemmatization phase was initiated. Lemmatization reduces words to their root forms, merging words with similar meanings, thus making the text more coherent. These processes enable machine learning models to process the texts more accurately and effectively. Raw texts usually contain unnecessary information and noise, which can negatively affect the models' performance.

```

1 # tokenization
2 def tokenize_text(text):
3     tokenizer = TurkishTokenizer.DEFAULT
4     tokens = tokenizer.tokenize(text)
5     token_list = [token.content for token in tokens]
6     return token_list

```

Figure 1. Tokenization function

A function was written for the tokenization process using the Turkish language library called "Zemberek."


```

1  # lemmatization
2  sentences = df_normalized['tokenized_text'].copy()
3
4  for token in sentences:
5      j = 0
6      for word in token:
7          new_word = (word.replace("'", ''))
8                      .replace('"', '')
9                      .replace(":", '')
10                     .replace(";", ''))
11
12         token[j] = new_word
13         j += 1
14
15  analyzer = zeyrek.MorphAnalyzer()
16  lem_sent = []
17  for sent in sentences:
18      normalized_sent = []
19      for word in sent:
20          if word == '':
21              continue
22          else:
23              lem_word = analyzer.lemmatize(word)
24              normalized_sent.append(lem_word[0][1][0])
25      lem_sent.append(normalized_sent)
26
27  x = lem_sent.copy()
28  for sent in x:
29      i = 0
30      for token in sent:
31          sent[i] = token.lower()
32          i += 1
33  lem_sent = x

```

Figure 2. Lemmatization function

A function was also written for the lemmatization process using the "Zemberek" library.

After applying the above text preprocessing steps, the data was simplified and cleaned, resulting in:

- Data free from noise and unnecessary information, providing a clearer and more meaningful dataset for analysis.
 - Cleaned and structured data that enables machine learning models to make more accurate predictions and analyses.
 - Simplified data that can reduce processing time and computational costs, offering more efficient analyses.
 - The merging of similar words in different forms, increasing the consistency of analysis results.
- After the data normalization phase, the processed texts remaining in the dataset are as follows:
- 1944 tweets remaining
 - 25254 words
 - An average of 13 words per tweet
 - 636 positive tweets, 1014 negative tweets, 294 neutral tweets

Figure 3. Pie chart of sentiment distribution

As can be understood from the pie chart above, the number of negative tweets had the highest percentage at 52%. Although the goal was to create a balanced dataset to optimize model performance, the numerical superiority of negative tweets was notable. This imbalance was addressed by generating synthetic data and giving more weight to certain sentiment categories.

Figure 4. Frequency of most repeated words

Feature Extraction

To accurately classify customer tweets, the processed tweets need to be converted into numerical representations, or vectors. For this purpose, the Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method, a statistical technique, was used. TF-IDF allows us to determine the relative importance of terms within documents and assigns a score based on their frequency in the text. These scores enable the models to produce results with higher performance and accuracy [1].

Term Frequency (TF) refers to the frequency of a specific word within a document. In this context, the entire dataset retrieved from X can be considered as the document. Term frequency is calculated by counting how often each term is used in the document.

$$TF(t, d) = \frac{\text{Number of Times Term Appears in Document}}{\text{Total Number of Terms in Document}} \quad (1)$$

Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) determines how common or rare a term is across all documents. More common terms have lower IDF values, while less common terms have higher IDF values. IDF measures the rarity of a specific term.

$$IDF(t) = \log \left(\frac{\text{Total Number of Documents}}{\text{Number of Documents Containing Term}} \right) \quad (2)$$

TF-IDF is a score obtained by multiplying term frequency (TF) and inverse document frequency (IDF). This score considers how important a specific term is in a document and how common it is across other documents. In this context, scores will be assigned based on the prevalence of terms among customer tweets. High TF-IDF scores indicate that the term is significant for that particular document but not common in other documents [2].

When examining Figure 2, it is observed that the most frequently occurring word is "olmak" (to be). Therefore, the TF-IDF score for the word "olmak" is the lowest.

$$TF - IDF(t, d) = TF(t, d) \times IDF(t) \quad (3)$$

Table 3. TF-IDF Scores from Lowest to Highest

Words	TF-IDF Score
"olmak"	2,68
"uçak"	2,77
"uçuşmak"	3,05
"iyi"	3,09
"kötü"	3,17

Model Creation

For classifying customer tweets, machine learning models such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Logistic Regression have been used. SVM is a powerful supervised learning algorithm that finds the optimal boundaries separating data points or identifying patterns. By representing text data as vectors in a high-dimensional space, SVMs provide effective separation between different text categories. They are particularly useful when labeled data is limited and often perform well with small to medium-sized datasets [3].

Figure 5. SVM Hyperplane

Logistic Regression is a powerful supervised learning algorithm widely used in classification problems. It is particularly effective when the dependent variable is categorical, aiming to model probabilities between classes using a linear function. In the context of Natural Language Processing (NLP), logistic regression proves effective in tasks such as text classification, sentiment analysis, and spam detection. By transforming text data into numerical features, it excels in distinguishing text categories. Moreover, its simplicity and interpretability enable high performance with small to medium-sized datasets.

Figure 6. Sigmoid Function

The above models will classify tweets into positive, negative, and neutral categories. To enhance model performance, the common parameter C was utilized in both models, with an additional specification of the 'linear' kernel for the SVM model. Hyperparameter tuning for the C parameter was conducted within the range of 0.1, 1, and 10, identifying 10 as the optimal value. The same approach applies to logistic regression. The dataset, comprised of customer tweets, was split into 80% for training and 20% for testing to train the models.

Model Evaluation

When analyzing the success rates of the classifications performed by the models, the SVM model outperformed the Logistic Regression model, achieving a slightly higher accuracy by 1%. During testing with the test set, the SVM model achieved an accuracy of 93%, while the Logistic Regression model achieved 92% accuracy.

Table 4. Confusion Matrix for SVM Model

Confusion Matrix			
label	precision	recall	f1-score
0	0.95	0.91	0.93
1	0.87	0.93	0.90
2	1	0.94	0.97
accuracy			0.93

Table 5. Confusion Matrix for Logistic Regression

Confusion Matrix			
label	precision	recall	f1-score
0	0.93	0.94	0.93
1	0.89	0.92	0.90
2		0.88	0.94
accuracy			0.92

Conclusion

In this project, tweets directed at the social media accounts, hashtags, and tags of Turkish airline companies by customers who have previously used their services were categorized into three emotional

classes: positive, negative, and neutral. Using SVM (Support Vector Machines) and logistic regression models, sentiment analysis was conducted. The SVM model demonstrated higher accuracy, achieving 93% accuracy compared to logistic regression. Additionally, natural language processing (NLP) techniques were employed to preprocess and analyze text data in this project.

When deployed in a live environment, these models can analyze and classify customer comments and tweets based on their emotional sentiments. Ultimately, the SVM model exhibited superior performance in sentiment analysis of social media data. These findings can contribute to airlines gaining better insights into customer feedback and potentially improving their services.

Table 6. Model classification evaluation in real-time deployment

Model Deployment		
Tweet	Model	Sentiment
"kabin amiri güler yüzlüydü, uçuşumuz çok rahat geçti"	SVM	1
	Logistic Regression	
"bir daha sizden bilet almam, hiç beğenmedim"	SVM	0
	Logistic Regression	
"yolculuk güzel fakat yemekler kötü"	SVM	2
	Logistic Regression	

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